

11th International Conference on Internet Engineering & Web Services (InWeS 2020)

December 19 ~ 20, 2020, Sydney, Australia

<https://iccsea2020.org/inwes/index.html>

Scope & Topics

11th International Conference on Internet Engineering & Web Services (InWeS 2020) will provide an excellent international forum for sharing knowledge and results in theory, methodology and applications of Internet Engineering & Web services environment. Current information age is witnessing a dramatic use of digital and electronic devices in the workplace and beyond. Internet Engineering & Web services present a rather arduous requirement of robustness, reliability and availability to the end user. Internet Engineering & Web services has received a significant and sustained research interest in terms of designing and deploying large scale and high performance computational applications in real life. The aim of the conference is to provide a platform to the researchers and practitioners from both academia as well as industry to meet and share cutting-edge development in the field.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following:

- Architectures and Frameworks
- Coding and Compression
- Collaborative Systems & Techniques
- Distance Learning
- E-business Modeling and Applications
- E-commerce Applications
- Fault Tolerance
- Information Retrieval
- Internet Architecture Design
- Internet Search Methods
- Internet Security & Applications
- Knowledge-Based Web Systems
- Multimedia Web Tools, Architectures, and Broadcasting
- Ontology and Web services
- Optimization Methods
- Security and Protection
- Semantic Web
- Software Agents
- Web Data Mining and Database Management
- Web Java-based Applications
- Web Languages
- Web Service Applications & Foundation
- Web Services-Driven Business Process Management
- Wireless & Mobile Based Applications, Services

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers through the conference [Submission system](#) by **July 18, 2020**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this conference. The proceedings of the conference will be published by [Computer Science Conference Proceedings](#) in [Computer Science & Information Technology \(CS & IT\)](#) series (Confirmed).

Selected papers from **InWes 2020**, after further revisions, will be published in the special issues of the following journals

- [International Journal of Web & Semantic Technology \(IJWesT\)](#)
- [International Journal on Web Service Computing \(IJWSC\)](#)
- [International Journal on Cloud Computing: Services and Architecture \(IJCCSA\)](#)
- [Information Technology in Industry \(ITI\)](#)^{New} - ESCI-Thomson Reuters Indexed, 2020.

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : July 18, 2020**
- Authors Notification : August 29, 2020
- Registration & Camera-Ready Paper Due : September 10, 2020

Contact Us

Here's where you can reach us : inwes@iccsea2019.org or inwesconference@yahoo.com